

Individualized Treatment & Service Plans: What have They to offer Individuals with Reading Challenges?

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this short paper is threefold: First, it is to provide readers with some basic understanding why individualized treatment and service plans came into place and their importance for children with special needs (also those with reading challenges), and also a brief introduction to the different types of individualized plans. Second, the authors want to introduce the Individualized Reading Plan and how it is designed basing on the results obtained from the administration of an informal reading inventory. Third, the main focus of this paper is to highlight to the readers the need to be mindful of the essential components in writing good Individualized Reading Plan (IRP), an equivalent of an Individualized Education Plan (IEP), using the proposed S.M.A.R.T. framework proposed by Chua (2016) with the need for properly written statements to define clearly the aims, goals and objectives for a child with reading challenges in his/her Individualized Reading Plan.

Key words: *individualized reading plan, reading, service, SMART framework, treatment*

INTRODUCTION

In the United States, the disability law is largely regulated by the Americans with Disabilities Act of 1990 (ADA) (also known as PL 103-230). Briefly, this Act has prohibited discrimination against individuals with disabilities in employment, housing education, and access to public services (e.g., public transport and barrier-free accessibility to places). The ADA defines a disability as any of the following:

- A physical or mental impairment that substantially limits one or more of the major life activities of the individual;
- A record of such impairment; or
- Being regarded as having such an impairment.

The ADA also required that reasonable accommodation be made so as to provide individuals with disabilities equal opportunities. However, the Act did not list all impairments covered until the introduction of Individuals with Disabilities Education Act 2004 (IDEA) and the subsequent ADA

Amendments Act of 2008 (ADAAA) (also known as PL 110-325). With the Act fully implemented, any state throughout the United States may introduce its own disability statutes provided they must be consistent with the ADAAA (Cornell University Law School, n.d., para.4).

The updated and revised ADA includes changes made by the ADA Amendments Act of 2008 (P.L. 110-325), which became effective on January 1, 2009. Originally enacted in public law format, the ADA was rearranged and published in the United States Code (USC), which is divided into titles and chapters that classify laws according to their subject matter. For example, the Titles I, II, III, and V of the original law are codified in Title 42, Chapter 126, of the USC beginning at section 12101 in Chapter 126 on Equal Opportunity for Individuals with Disabilities (p.4). Title IV of the original law is codified in Title 47, Chapter 5, of the USC.

When the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) was signed into law on December 3, 2004, the provisions of the Act became effective on July 1, 2005, with the exception of some of the elements pertaining to the definition of a “highly qualified” teacher that took effect upon the signing of the Act. With the implementation of IDEA, individuals with disabilities are identified and given necessary treatments and appropriate special services designed to meet their unique needs. Early intervention is now available for infants and toddlers with disabilities under three years of age and their families. “For school-age children and youth (aged 3 through 21), special education and related services are provided through the school system” (National Dissemination Center for Children with Disabilities, 2012, p.1).

Besides the United States, other English-speaking countries such as the United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand have also introduced their own respective laws to protect the interests and well-being of their citizens with disabilities. In Canada, in accordance with Regulation 181/98 of the Education Act, all school boards throughout Ontario, for an example, must meet the required standards when developing, implementing, and monitoring Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) for students with disabilities as well as for students not identified as having disabilities but who are also receiving a special education program and services.

However, in Asia and South-east Asia, such laws have not been properly introduced, passed by the parliaments of respective countries or implemented. In most instances, the authors personally felt that it is more an issue of lacking the political will to see through such Act being passed and implemented. Most, if not all, Asian countries are still in the process of developing their own legislative guidelines to meet the sociocultural needs of their own people with disabilities. Although most countries throughout the world as well as those in Asia have introduced Compulsory Education Act to ensure their children receive at least elementary education with the necessary knowledge and skills for their survival in the working world, not the same attention has been paid to children, youth or adults with special needs (or disabilities). Hence, unlike the United States, where Individualized Education Plan (IEP) or Individualized Treatment Plan (ITP) is mandatory for every child with disability, it is not practised in most, if not all, Asian countries.

TREATMENT FOR INDIVIDUALS WITH READING CHALLENGES

When we speak of individuals with disabilities, we refer to those “experiencing developmental delays, as measured by appropriate diagnostic instruments and procedures, in one or more of the following areas: cognitive development, physical development, communication development,

socio-emotional development, and adaptive development; or have a diagnosed physical or mental condition that has a high probability of resulting in developmental delay” (National Dissemination Center for Children with Disabilities, 2012, p.1). There are “thirteen categories of disability listed in IDEA: autism, deaf-blindness, emotional disturbance, hearing impairment, intellectual disability, multiple disabilities, orthopedic impairment, other health impairment, specific learning disability, speech or language impairment, traumatic brain injury, or visual impairment (including blindness)” (National Dissemination Center for Children with Disabilities, 2012, p.1-2). Reading challenges (also use interchangeably with terms like difficulties, disabilities and disorders) can be classified under specific learning disability. The Educator’s Diagnostic Manual of Disabilities and Disorders (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2007) is a good resourcebook where teachers and other educational professionals such as reading specialists and educational therapists can turn to for reference and find out the specific disabilities and their subtypes for each of the IDEA disability categories.

As required by IDEA, once an individual has been diagnosed with a disability listed on the IDEA disability list, the next step is to prepare an individualized treatment plan (ITP) for an appropriate treatment to address the issues (learning and/or behavioral) of concern. An Individualized Treatment Plan (ITP) is a tool used by therapists, interventionists, and/or other professionals and paraprofessionals with their client (or patient, a term that we would prefer not to use) to shape the focus of treatment for the client’s cognitive, conative, affective and/or sensory as well as mental issues of concern. The ITP helps the therapists and clients make positive change happen through purpose, focus and direction. It is like a road map that the client will follow on his/her journey through treatment for a specified duration where the relapse rates drop to around zero. Treatment planning begins as soon as the initial assessments are completed. The client might have immediate needs that must be addressed. Treatment planning is a never-ending stream of therapeutic plans and interventions, always moving and changing.

When we talk about the term *treatment*, we are not talking about “cure”, which means the client no longer has that particular condition anymore. Treatment must never be equated to cure. Instead, we are referring to three types of care: (1) intervention; (2) rehabilitation; and (3) management. Briefly, we define intervention as a systematic process of careful observation, diagnostic assessment and planning employed to remediate or prevent a social, educational or developmental problem from becoming worse. There are six levels of intervention: pre-emptive, preventive, corrective, remedial, compensatory, and complimentary/alternative, but this will not be covered in this paper. Rehabilitation is the second form of treatment. We define it as an approach designed to facilitate the discovery process of a client from injury, illness, or disease to as normal a condition as possible. The purpose of rehabilitation is to restore some or all of the client’s physical, sensory and mental capabilities back to their norms where possible, and may include compensating for deficits that cannot be reversed. Rehabilitation should be administered only by relevant qualified therapists. Management, unlike intervention and rehabilitation, is a collaborative process involving a transdisciplinary team of professionals to deliver a long-term course of multiple treatment regimes linking the client examination and diagnosis to resolution of the client’s presenting chronic or lifelong condition.

SERVICES FOR INDIVIDUALS WITH READING CHALLENGES

In the profession of reading specialists (NOT reading therapists), we avoid using terms like disabilities or disorders and more in favor of terms like challenges in cognition, conation, affect and sensation, resulting in the recognition of learning problems and response in terms of behavior (conation) and emotion (affect) through our various senses (sensation). For each of these problems, different types of services will be needed. Hence, in treatment, the services to be provided must include proper interview, assessment, consultation, planning, intervention and evaluation. We need to do a thorough treatment as well as service planning in order to benefit the client with reading challenges. This means that a proper Individualized Service Plan (just like the Individualized Family Service Plan required by IDEA for any family that has a child with disability) must be prepared for the client to know exactly the kind of service needed for treatment.

The Individualized Service Plan (ISP) can be divided into two levels. The first level involves a proper developmental design of a client management plan and it includes the following: (1) interview or consultation; (2) assessment and profiling; (3) follow-up or further consultation; (4) type of treatment planning (including annual aim, semester goals and term objectives); (5) implementation of the treatment; and finally, (6) evaluation of the treatment progress to determine how much has been achieved by the client from the treatment to meet the aim, goals and objectives as set. The second level concerns the written details of the supports, activities, and resources required for the client with special needs to achieve personal goals. The ISP is developed to articulate decisions and agreements made during a person-centered process of planning and information gathering. The general welfare and personal preferences of the individual are the key consideration in the development of all plans.

INDIVIDUALIZED READING PLAN

There are many different treatment and service plans. The most familiar ones among these plans are the Individualized Education Plan (IEP) and the Individualized Family Service Plan (IFSP). Others include Individualized Training Plan (ITgP), Individualized Transition Plan (ITnP), Individualized Care Plan (ICP), Individualized Counseling Plan (ICoP), Individualized Healthcare Management Plan (IHCMP), Community Service Plan (ICoMP), Individualized Reading Plan (IRP) and the list goes on. However, not all the different plans are mandatory by the Disability Law in the United States. Some of the non-mandatory plans are being strongly advocated by different groups of professionals, e.g., the Reading Specialists will advocate for IRP, the Counselors will go for ICoP, while the job coaches go for ITgP. In this paper, our focus is on the Individualized Reading Plan.

Ideally speaking, if a client has a severe reading challenge (e.g., a severe degree of being dyslexic or rather, we should say, a serious form of reading challenge in being unable to recognize words), we certainly need both the ITP and ISP as described earlier. The ITP will be the IRP, like IEP, and it can be designed by a teacher or an allied educator (as well as resource teacher or reading specialist) in consultation with the child's family. The ISP will be like the IFSP but with a special attention on reading development and it can be designed collaboratively by a social service coordinator in consultation with the client's family as well as other professionals, especially a reading specialist. Finally, the ICSP will be most helpful if there is a case manager to focus on the additional helps that will benefit the client's reading development and explore all the resources

(e.g., trade books that can be borrowed from a public or community library), programs (e.g., the national KidsREAD program initiated by the National Library Board for at-risk readers coming from low-income families in Singapore) and services (e.g., librarians-on-duty who advise and provide assistance in sourcing out age-appropriate books) available in the community. When all these three plans, i.e., IRP/IEP, ISF/IFSP and ICSP, are put together, they help to triangulate the resources, programs, services and expertise available to cater to learning & behavioral needs of an individual with reading challenges (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Triangulation of IEP, IFSP and ICSP

At this juncture, we want to provide our definition of an Individualized Reading Plan (IRP), adapted from that of an IEP, as a written plan describing the reading program and/or services required by an individual with reading difficulties. It identifies reading expectations that are modified from or alternative to the expectations given in the reading curriculum policy document for the appropriate grade and subject or course, and/or any accommodations and access arrangement services needed to assist the individual in achieving his/her reading expectations. The IRPs of those readers who have no modified or alternative expectations will focus only on accommodations and ancillary services they need.

We want to reiterate that the IRP is not a daily lesson plan itemizing every detail of the individual's reading development. However, it will certainly help teachers and allied educators (or tutors) to monitor the progress of poor, disadvantaged, reluctant or disabled readers and provides a framework for communicating information about these readers' respective progresses to their parents or guardians and also to the individual himself/herself.

The IRP should be updated periodically by the teacher or allied educator (or even the reading specialist who is working directly with the individual), if it is to be useful, to record any changes in the individual's reading program and services that are found to be necessary as a result of continuous assessment and evaluation of the student's reading achievement in terms of annual goals and reading expectations.

At the school level, the IRP reflects the commitment of the school board and/or the school principal to provide special reading program (e.g., letting at-risk readers to participate in a buddy reading program 20 minutes before and after school hours), allotted reading places (e.g., reading corner with low coffee tables and cosy couches) and services (e.g., school library should be open for children to borrow and return books during recess or after school), within the school with resources available to the school board, needed to meet the identified strengths and needs of the readers. The

school principal is responsible for ensuring compliance with all of the requirements described in the document prepared by the school administration (e.g., the English Language Department) for the development and implementation of the IRPs for at-risk readers.

S.M.A.R.T. FRAMEWORK FOR WRITING ATTAINABLE OBJECTIVES IN AN INDIVIDUALIZED READING PLAN

Perhaps the most tedious part in writing a good attainable IRP is coming up with tangible learning (or reading) objectives. When an IRP is to be implemented in school, it is important to take note that there are differences among aims, goals and objectives. When we talk about aim, we refer to an annual aim for IRP, i.e., what we hope for the individual to achieve at the end of the year. This will become the main guidepost for the entire IRP to move on from the beginning to the end of the year without straying away from the original purpose. There will be two goals for IRP: Semester 1 goal and Semester 2 goal. The two goals should serve as intermediate benchmarks between the annual aim and the four term objectives. The Semester 1 goal will cover the first part of the annual aim from January to June; the Semester 2 goal, the second part of the annual aim from July to December. Then there should be some form of transitional goal from Semester 1 goal to Semester 2 goal to show the link between the two semestral goals that are aligned with the annual aim. The objectives are more specific and they cover all the four terms of the school year. Each objective covers a term of ten weeks. Terms 1 and 2 objectives should align with the Semester 1 goal, while Terms 3 and 4 should align with the Semester 2 goal (see Figure 2). There should also be a smooth transition objective clearly stated from Term 1 objective moving to Term 2 objective and so on. Each objective can be subdivided further into the learning component and the behavioral component. For example: By the end of Term 1, the child should be able to read Grade 4 readers with 95% of accuracy in word recognition (learning) without using his index finger at all to point at each word as he reads (behavioral).

Figure 2. Annual Aim, Semester Goals and Term Objectives

When writing IRPs (or IEPs), most reading professionals should be aware of using S.M.A.R.T. approach in formulating their aims, goals and objectives, where S: Specific, M: Measurable; A: Use action words; R: Realistic and relevant; and T: Time-limited. However, for goals to be meaningful and functional, it is never an easy task to formulate them. To do well in goal setting or writing, it requires time and effort with a lot of practice. Chua (2016) has proposed using the same acronym S.M.A.R.T. with different denotation – S: Specificity, M: Meaningful, A: Appropriateness, R: Routine-based, and T: Transferability – as a framework, and in this case, for reading educators and reading specialists in designing IRPs. To quote loosely from Chua (2016, p.2), we “use of this framework is to improve the quality of written IRP goals of individuals with reading challenges” (IEP is replaced with IRP in this quotation).

We have described each of the five factors of S.M.A.R.T. briefly below:

S stands for Specificity. Reading professionals should know that, like IEPs, IRPs are also meant to be issued to parents so that they know what treatment and services are provided to help their children with reading challenges. The annual aim, semesteral goals and term objectives (we have abbreviated these terms to AA-SG-TO to be used for the rest of this paper) should be clearly and simply written in plain English so that every parent regardless of his/her literacy level can make sense of the document. Linguistic or technical terms and jargons should be avoided or totally dropped from the IRP. For example, instead of using the term *cacographia* in the IRP, just write “untidy handwriting.” That is easier to understand for most parents.

M stands for Meaningful. For any IRP to be useful to any layman (e.g., parents) other than the reading professionals themselves to read, understand and know to do, AA-SG-TO must be functionally meaningful, otherwise, the document is going to be a white elephant to be put away in the child’s personal record file. Be functionally meaningful, we mean the AA-SG-TO is understood meaningfully to be carried out functionally. For example, by the end of the first week, the child will be able to recognize a list of 15 sight words taken from a Grade 1 reader by pointing correctly to each of the 15 target words read to him. From this objective, what must the child be able to do? Functionally, he child be able to (1) recognize all 15 words provided on a list and (2) point to the target word read to him. To do so all these words must be meaningful to the child, and they are because these words are taken from a grade 1 reader that the child is familiar or has read before.

A stands for Appropriateness. AA-SG-TO formulated by the reading professionals must be developmentally appropriate for the child. By developmentally appropriate, we do not mean age appropriate because there are always those who may be chronologically older but are reading at a level a few years below their biological age. In other words, the IRP must be designed to meet the cognitive potential of an individual with or without reading challenges at his/her mental age. For example, a 10-year-old child is able to read books for 8-year-old readers. Logically speaking, the child will be considered a backward reader, two years behind what a 10-year-old should be reading. However, if the same child has a mental age of 8 years, then we can say the book is developmentally appropriate for him because that is his actual cognitive potential in reading.

R stands for Routine-based. The design of IRP must always take into consideration a child’s daily routines (e.g., home, school, community) because such routine activities are what the child normally does in his/her real daily living. The parents should be able to provide the daily timetable to the professionals who are referring to the IRP to work with the child. According to Chua (2016), “the provision of learning in natural environments effectively promote children’s development as compared to traditional intervention models provided in specialized programs” (p.3). Moreover, “routines that occur within natural settings for children provides effective framework to support and sustain early intervention activities” (Chua, 2016, p.3). Chua (2016) has also reiterated that “[W]hen classroom activities are embedded into children’s daily routines and activities, both children and their caregivers will learn skills that are both meaningful and functional” (p.3).

T stands for Transferability. This is the last factor. It points to the importance of being able to apply what has been taught to or learnt by a child must be transferable from one context to other contexts. “In other words, what the child learns in the school can also be transferred to home, childcare center, and the community” (Chua 2016, p.3). For example, the Carnine scheme of letter names is used by a reading specialist to teach letter knowledge to a child, who has never been exposed to the English Alphabet. The Carnine letter scheme is used because it is based on the sequence of letters that are most commonly encountered in print and environment. If the child is able to recite from Aa to Zz but cannot even read KFC off the fast food restaurant signboard in front of him, he has definitely failed to transfer the letter knowledge he has acquired to his present setting.

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